

2Pipe: It starts with a question. Matching you with the correct pipeline for MAG reconstruction

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Descriptive pipeline overview

Below we present a descriptive overview of the main workflow for each pipeline or platform, where important technical considerations such as the type of input (short reads, long reads or both), key tools employed at each step, advantages, limitations and/or special features they depict are documented.

1. Short-read centered pipelines

1.1 Anvi'o¹

Anvi'o is a comprehensive modular platform for the analysis and visualization of microbial omics including, but not restricted to, metagenomics, metatranscriptomics and metapangenomics. Anvi'o is developed to be highly customizable through exchangeable programs (tools) that perform specific tasks, empowering the user with a wide range of tools to explore. Being so, a metagenomics workflow is proposed by the developers of the platforms that begins with short-read quality cleaning, proceeds to read assembly to be used for read recruitment (mapping), and finalizes contig annotation (functions, Hidden Markov Models, and taxonomy). Optionally, the user can achieve read taxonomic profiling with KrakenUniq², and more recently binning tools have been made available such as MetaBAT³, CONCOCT⁴, MaxBin⁵ and BinSanity⁶, as well as DASTool⁷ as a refinement alternative. Nonetheless, the user must run the analysis manually, requiring them to account with some experience regarding software installation, execution and debugging. Moreover, although Anvi'o is in principle a command line tool, it incorporates a user-friendly graphical interface for data inspection and visualization that is commonly used for contig visualization.

1.2 BugBuster⁸

BugBuster is an automatic, modular, and reproducible Nextflow⁹ (DSL2) workflow with specialized modules for taxonomic profiling and resistome characterization. Its workflow encompasses the following steps: initial reads processing for quality filtering and host contamination removal (Bowtie¹⁰); taxonomic profiling at the read level using tools like Kraken¹¹/Bracken¹² or Sourmash¹³; and antibiotic resistance gene (ARG) prediction from reads using KARGA¹⁴ and KARGVA¹⁵. The assembly is carried out with MEGAHIT¹⁶, followed by taxonomic and functional annotation of contigs using BLAST¹⁷, BlobTools¹⁸, DeepARG¹⁹, and MetaCerberus²⁰. Afterwards, the contigs are binned with tools such as MetaBAT³, SemiBin²¹ and COMEBin²², and refined them with a MetaWRAP²³-native module; the quality is assessed with CheckM²⁴, and the MAGs are taxonomically affiliated with GTDB-Tk²⁵. BugBuster is fully containerized (Docker) aiming at ensuring ease of installation, high reproducibility, and deployment across various computational environments. Moreover, BugBuster stands out given its inclusion of specific tools to characterize and quantify genes associated with antibiotic resistance.

1.3 DATMA²⁶

DATMA (Distributed AuTomatic Metagenomic Assembly and annotation framework) is a pipeline focused on speed and automation, leveraging distributed computing for efficiency. As a

starting point, DATMA applies a quality filter with RAPPILFILT (customized tool developed for this pipeline), Trimmomatic²⁷ and FastQC²⁸, and if the input sequences are paired-end, it merges them using FLASH2²⁹ and ForceMerge. Following this procedure, this pipeline identifies and removes 16S rDNA sequences based on RFAM³⁰ (RNA sequence families), NCBI³¹, Ribosomal Database Project (RDP)³² and SILVA³³ to cluster the remaining sequences with CLAME³⁴. The clusters (or bins in definition of the traditional workflow) generated then are assembled in batches by metaSPAdes³⁵, Velvet³⁶, and MEGAHIT¹⁶ for a subsequent taxonomic annotation relying on BLAST³⁷ and Kaiju³⁸, as well as ORF prediction with Prodigal³⁹ and GeneMark⁴⁰. To conclude with the analysis a detailed HTML report is generated with interactive Krona⁴¹ plots for taxonomic visualization; this report integrates the 16S rDNA annotation (RDP Classified) along with the annotated bins. As inferred from the described workflow, DATMA performs an inverted approach to generate bins by first grouping the reads using CLAME and attempting to assemble only these groups individually afterwards. Further, this pipeline is wrapped by COMP Superscalar which facilitates the development and execution of parallel applications for distributed infrastructures such as clusters, cloud services and containerized platforms.

1.4 EasyMetagenome⁴²

EasyMetagenome integrates a classical workflow starting with short reads to provide a de-replicated (dRep⁴³) set of bins and pangenome analysis that relies on an Anvi'o module. The assembly is performed with MEGAHIT¹⁶, a MetaWRAP²³ module is in charge of the binning task, CheckM2²⁴ controls the quality of the bins, and GTDB-Tk2²⁵ finalizes the execution by taxonomically annotating them. Notably, this pipeline performs functional annotation (GhostKOALA⁴⁴, eggNOG⁴⁵, dbCAN3⁴⁶) and taxonomy assignment on the contigs after a pre-filtering step that generates a non-redundant gene set. EasyMetagenome uses Conda environments to assure reproducibility, the user can input multi-sample data, although it is not orchestrated by any workflow manager. As special remarks, it carries out a taxonomic profiling (MetaPhlan⁴⁷, HUMAnN3⁴⁸, Kraken2¹¹) of the post-filtered (KneadData) reads, and the functional annotation of the gene set is expanded to identify virulence factors (VFDB⁴⁹) and antibiotic resistant genes (CARD⁵⁰).

1.5 EURYALE (MEDUSA)^{51,52}

EURYALE is a Nextflow-based reimplement of the MEDUSA pipeline. It provides a modular and containerized workflow using Nextflow DSL2, with software execution through Docker, Conda or Singularity, which ensures portability, reproducibility, and scalability. The workflow of this pipeline starts with read quality control with FastQC²⁸, trimming and merging using fastp⁵³, and optional host decontamination with Bowtie2¹⁰; MultiQC⁵⁴ provides a full report containing visualizations regarding sequence preprocessing. Optionally, clean sequences can be assembled using MEGAHIT¹⁶ with a posterior taxonomic classification carried out by Kaiju³⁸ or Kraken2¹¹, while functional annotation relies on a DIAMOND⁵⁵-based alignment to reference databases (NCBI nr by default). It is worthy to mention the flexibility EURYALE offers given its customizable database selection for both taxonomic and functional annotation.

1.6 JAMS⁵⁶

JAMS (Just a Microbiology System) is an integrated framework originally designed to perform the analysis on the NIH's Biowulf system. JAMS is divided into two main modules: JAMS α , which performs single sample analyses, and JAMS β , which focuses on cross-sample comparisons. JAMS α (the pipeline) integrates tools such as Bowtie2¹⁰ for host removal, MEGAHIT¹⁶ or SPAdes⁵⁷ for read assembly, Kraken2¹¹ for taxonomic classification, and Prokka⁵⁸ and InterProScan⁵⁹ for gene and protein domain prediction, respectively; JAMS β uses R-based packages for visualization and statistical analysis. This workflow is executed within Conda environments, and its main advantage relies on the ease to establish comparisons across samples. However, this pipeline does not support binning tools nor genome-quality, and currently, it exhibits restricted deployment flexibility due to optimization for the NIH's Biowulf system, although JAMS is open source and can be installed on any UNIX-based machine.

1.7 MAGNETO⁶⁰

MAGNETO is an automated, modularized and scalable pipeline wrapped with Snakemake⁶¹ and executed with Conda. It is focused on allowing the user the selection of different assembly and/or binning strategies, involving several steps from read pre-processing until MAG annotation and gene catalog generation. The *Pre-processing* module leverages fastp⁵³, Bowtie2¹⁰ and FastQ Screen⁶², whilst the *Assembly* mode uses Simka⁶³ and hierarchical agglomerative clustering to cluster the samples if the users pre-defines a co-assembly strategy; the reads are assembled using MEGAHIT¹⁶. Furthermore, contig abundances are computed by alignment against the raw reads to be bin by MetaBAT2³ afterwards. Quality estimation and dereplication are carried out with CheckM⁶⁴ v1.0 and dRep⁴³, respectively. To end the workflow, a gene catalog is produced for both the contigs and the MAGs by running Prodigal³⁹, Linclust⁶⁵ and CD-HIT⁶⁶, and the MAGs are annotated with GTDB-Tk2²⁵ and eggNOG-mapper⁶⁷. As a special feature, MAGNETO can provide a read-based taxonomy abundance with mOTU⁶⁸ profiler. MAGNETO exhibits all the advantages Snakemake wrapping, and executed with Conda, represents such as multi-sample handling, scalability across different computing infrastructures and checkpoint control for workflow restarting.

1.8 MAGO⁶⁹

MAGO is an end-to-end pipeline designed to run over a single execution from a container image (Singularity or Docker); a third option is available as a Virtual Machine (VM). This configuration allows MAGO to offer a streamlined implementation of the entire metagenomics pipeline, including error checking, and computational resource distribution. The tool workflow follows the traditional design with read quality control (fastp⁵³, FastQC²⁸), followed by the assembly step with MEGAHIT¹⁶, metaSPAdes³⁵ and/or IBDA-UD⁷⁰. MAGO performs binning through multiple algorithms (MetaBAT⁷¹, MaxBin2⁵, CONCOCT⁴ and BinSanity with multiple configurations). MAG completeness and contamination of MAGs are estimated with CheckM⁶⁴. To conclude the execution, MAGO annotates the MAGs with Prokka⁵⁸, and performs taxonomic classification and phylogenetic placement using GTDB-Tk⁷². Moreover, to expand its capabilities, the developers included the possibility of generating phylogenetic trees through ezTree⁷³, analyzing the pangenome with Roary and measuring ANI with FastANI⁷⁴ as an approximation to de-replicate the MAG set.

1.9 metaGEM⁷⁵

metaGEM represents a traditional end-to-end pipeline designed to reconstruct MAGs from metagenomics raw reads; however, its main feature relies on an integrated module that provides genome scale metabolic models (GEMS). The workflow starts with the read quality cleaning using fastp⁵³ for a subsequent assembly with MEGAHIT¹⁶ and a contig coverage estimation with BWA⁷⁶. The bins are then obtained via three different tools (MetaBAT2³, MaxBin2⁵ and CONCOCT⁴) along a posterior refining by the metaWRAP²³ refinement module. As a result, the bins or MAGs are used as input for CarveMe⁷⁷ (Genome Scale Metabolic Models), and SMETANA⁷⁸ is called for metabolic interaction predictions and MEMOTE⁷⁹ is in charge of generating quality reports. The resulting GEMs can then be used for various downstream analyses, such as predicting metabolic interactions within the community, simulating growth under different conditions, and identifying key metabolic pathways. The pipeline ends with MAG characterization through Prokka⁵⁸ and Roary⁸⁰ (functional annotation and pangenome analysis), GRiD⁸¹ (growth rate estimation), GTDB-Tk2²⁵ (taxonomic annotation) and BWA⁷⁶ (genome abundance). As additional features, metaGEM identifies eukaryotic MAGs via EukRep⁸² and evaluates contamination with EukCC⁸³. Also, this pipeline produces taxonomic abundance profiles from the filtered reads using mOTUS2⁸⁴. Naturally, this pipeline exhibits the benefits Snakemake⁶¹ orchestration provides, as mentioned previously.

1.10 MetaGenePipe⁸⁵

MetaGenePipe is a pipeline developed with Workflow Definition Language (WDL), self-executed within a Singularity container, whose primary goal is performing a contig-based functional and taxonomic analysis from short read sequences. It is composed of 4 subworkflows, where the

operation starts with the quality control workflow, the subsequent one assembles the reads with MEGAHIT¹⁶ to map them back against the short reads within the third subworkflow. Meanwhile, the last subworkflow is in charge of gene prediction and functional annotation based on two main strategies: alignment with the Swiss-Prot database and Hidden Markov Models search in KOfam database⁸⁶. Although MetaGenePipe does not include binning software to provide MAGs as main output, its versatility that allows an analysis adapted for eukaryotic and viral analyses with minimal modifications, and its uncommon workflow manager within the pipelines considered in this review, makes MetaGenePipe an interesting alternative for users with advanced computational infrastructures. Additionally, MetaGenePipe is designed to handle a co-assembly strategy in case the user requires this feature.

1.12 Metagenome-Atlas⁸⁷

Metagenome-Atlas is an end-to-end, Snakemake⁶¹-based and Conda-executed pipeline supporting Illumina short reads and providing a modular workflow. It is divided into four modules, namely Quality Control, Assembly, Genomic Binning and Annotation. The initial module removes host, common contaminants and PCR duplicates, and if necessary, trims low-quality sequences according to user pre-specified parameters. The Assembly module corrects sequence errors based on k-mer coverage, merges paired-end sequences, assembles them using MEGAHIT¹⁶ and/or metaSPAdes³⁵ along with a contig-length filtering. The following module uses MetaBAT2³, MaxBin2⁵, and optionally VAMB⁸⁸ and SemiBin2²¹ to bin the contigs; CheckM2²⁴, BUSCO⁸⁹ and GUNC⁹⁰ are run to measure the bin quality, as well as DASTool⁷ and dRep⁴³ for bin refinement and MAG dereplication, respectively. For the last module, Metagenome-Atlas taxonomically and functionally annotates the MAGs using GTDB-Tk2²⁵ and DRAM⁹¹, respectively, and it finally produces a gene catalog through mapping the predicted coding sequences using eggNOG-mapper⁶⁷. Among the main advantages of Metagenome-Atlas, it is possible to describe the possibility of running individual modules and its energetic supporting community and developers. Moreover, the Snakemake wrapper allows for flexibility, multi-sample handling, and adaptability to medium to large projects running on local servers or High-Performance Cluster (HPC) environments.

1.13 Metaphor⁹²

Metaphor is a classic metagenomics pipeline aiming at MAG reconstruction and annotation wrapped by Snakemake⁶¹ and leveraging Conda as package manager. The pipeline is triggered by the user with a .csv file pointing to the sequence directories and a .yaml file with the pipeline configuration. A quality control will be carried out then with FastQC²⁸ and fastp⁵³, with a posterior assembly with MEGAHIT¹⁶, contig evaluation with MetaQUAST⁹³ and mapping against the input sequences using Minimap2⁹⁴ and Samtools; the contigs are binned (VAMB⁸⁸, MetaBAT2³, CONCOCT⁴) and refined (DASTool⁷). Metaphor execution finalizes with bin annotation through Prodigal, Diamond, and the NCBI COG database. Complementary to Snakemake orchestration capabilities, Metaphor provides a series of plots depicting runtime and memory with the goal of identifying computational bottlenecks during the analyses.

1.14 MetaWRAP²³

MetaWRAP is a popular and customizable pipeline built primarily as a command-line framework with a focus on flexibility and user control. MetaWRAP consists of individual modules that can be run independently or combined into custom workflows. Its core functionalities encompasses read QC and cleaning (FastQC²⁸, Trim Galore and BMTagger), assembly (MEGAHIT¹⁶, metaSPAdes³⁵, BWA⁷⁶ and MetaQUAST⁹³), and a binning suite that incorporates MetaBAT2³, MaxBin2⁵, and CONCOCT⁴. MetaWRAP also includes a native refinement module that produces hybrid bin sets to explore over the different variants of each bin (original and hybridized bin sets) to determine the “best bin” according to the user pre-specified quality values based on completeness and contamination (CheckM⁶⁴ v1.0). This module is frequently executed in independent metagenomics analysis, and even some pipelines described in this review incorporate it within their workflows. If decided by the user, MetaWRAP offers the possibility of bin re-assembling guided by their previous versions, improving the overall bin quality. For MAG taxonomic and functional analysis, MetaWRAP relies on Prokka⁵⁸ and

Taxator-tk⁹⁵ (combined with NCBI³¹ databases), and it provides visualization modules for summarizing results. Analogous to MAGNETO⁶⁰, MetaWRAP can produce read-based taxonomic profiles in parallel. Although MetaWRAP does not integrate full pipeline automation, its high modularity and straightforward design have promoted a wide supporting community. Nonetheless, at the moment of writing this report, MetaWRAP is not maintained by the developers, with the subsequent lack of tool updates.

Nonetheless, given the popularity of MetaWRAP, a Snakemake⁶¹ wrapper was developed to automate the metagenomics analysis known as SnakeWRAP⁹⁶. Therefore, SnakeWRAP can carry out the MetaWRAP end-to-end read processing to generate MAGs in a single run, retaining the flexibility of MetaWRAP while reducing the burden of manual execution and dependency handling. Additionally, SnakeWRAP's integrated environment management via Conda and support for HPC environments enables seamless execution of multiple MetaWRAP modules and samples in parallel, being particularly useful for multi-sample execution.

1.15 MOSHPIT⁹⁷

According to its documentation, *MOSHPIT (MOdular SHotgun metagenome Pipelines with Integrated provenance Tracking)* is a toolkit of plugins for whole metagenome assembly, annotation, and analysis built on the microbiome multi-omics data science framework QIIME 2⁹⁸. *MOSHPIT enables flexible, modular, fully reproducible workflows for read-based or assembly-based analysis of metagenome data.* The core components of MOSHPIT include q2-assembly, which provides functionalities for genome assembly and quality control, and q2-annotate, which supports contig binning, taxonomic classification, and functional annotation. Additional plugins, such as q2-viromics and q2-amrfinderplus, extend capabilities to viral sequence detection and antimicrobial resistance gene annotation, respectively. In technical terms, MOSHPIT must be run locally or on an HPC environment with the possibility to execute the processes in parallel by the explicit declaration of partitions, a native QIIME2 functionality. Further, the entire QIIME2 ecosystem relies on Conda, and hence this a *sine-qua-non* requisite to perform MAG reconstruction with MOSHPIT.

1.16 nIMP3⁹⁹

nIMP3 is a Nextflow-based reimplementation of the IMP (Integrated Meta-omic Pipeline) workflow that assembles metagenomics (MG) and metatranscriptomics (MT) datasets together. nIMP3 handles preprocessed and contaminant-free MT and MG reads (FastQC²⁸, SortMeRNA¹⁰⁰, BBTools¹⁰¹), and jointly assembles them in a *hybrid* and iterative process using MEGAHIT¹⁶. Additionally, nIMP3 performs taxonomic profiling with mOTUs¹⁰² and Kraken2¹¹, as well as functional profiling with gffquant¹⁰³. Unlike the original IMP pipeline, nIMP3 does not include a binning module, and thus it cannot recover MAGs. Nonetheless, nIMP3 offers a lighter, reproducible, and integrative pipeline for multi-omics metagenome/metatranscriptome processing.

1.17 SnakeMAGs¹⁰⁴

SnakeMAGs is a simple yet useful pipeline that as its name indicates is controlled by a Snakemake⁶¹ wrapper with Conda as software administrator. It integrates basic modules starting with quality control with Illumina-utils¹⁰⁵ and Trimmomatic²⁷, and if required, host removal with Bowtie2¹⁰. Afterwards, the reads are assembled through MEGAHIT¹⁶, the contigs are binned by MetaBAT2³, a quality assessment is carried out with CheckM⁶⁴ v1.1 and GUNC⁹⁰, MAG abundances are obtained using CoverM¹⁰⁶, and finally the taxonomic classification is performed using GTDB-Tk2²⁵. Similar to the previous pipelines governed by Snakemake, SnakeMAGs eases automation, reproducibility, scalability and workflow management.

1.18 SPIRE¹⁰⁷

The SPIRE project employs a Nextflow-based pipeline that has been used to process and annotate more than 100,000 metagenomes belonging to more than 700 studies. The workflow incorporates tools such as NGLess¹⁰⁸ for read trimming and decontamination, MEGAHIT¹⁶ for

assembly, Prodigal³⁹ for gene prediction and barrnap¹⁰⁹ for ribosomal RNA detection. Moreover, contig binning is carried out with MetaBAT2³ with a complementary genome quality assessment using CheckM2²⁴ and GUNC⁹⁰, and the workflow ends with taxonomic classification (GTDB-Tk2²⁵) and functional annotation (eggNOG-mapper⁶⁷, abricate¹¹⁰, RGI⁵⁰ and Macrel¹¹¹). Among the advantages SPIRE offers, the possibility to perform antimicrobial resistance gene prediction and the annotation of virulence factors stand out, as well as its scalability, reproducibility across high-performance and cloud environments, and standardized processing, enabling consistent comparisons across global datasets. Nonetheless, at the moment of writing this report, this pipeline is aiming to be executed at online platforms like CloWM¹¹² as it is lacking defined environments or container images, and the input data should be already hosted at the sequencing archives such as ENA, DDBJ or SRA.

1.19 Sunbeam¹¹³

Sunbeam is a modular pipeline orchestrated by Snakemake⁶¹ with Conda as dependency manager; this configuration makes Sunbeam analysis reliable, reproducible and scalable. The main feature Sunbeam depicts is its modularized and extensible design that allows users to build off the core functionality. The execution backbone of Sunbeam is represented by an initial quality control that encloses adapter trimming, host read removal and low-complexity filtering (Trimmomatic²⁷, FastQC²⁸, BWA⁷⁶ and Komplexity), followed the assembly of reads into contigs with MEGAHIT¹⁶ along with their corresponding annotation with Prodigal³⁹, BLAST³⁷ and Diamond⁵⁵ (with nucleotide or protein databases). As complementary procedures, Sunbeam maps the reads to reference genomes (user pre-specified) and delivers a taxonomic assignment of the clean reads using Kraken¹¹⁴ v1.0. As previously stated, its modularization and ready-to-use templates to create new modules have enabled the development of additional extensions for assigning metagenomic reads to a full bacterial phylogeny, single genome assembly, among others.

2. Long-read focused pipelines

2.1 EasyNanoMeta¹¹⁵

EasyNanoMeta is a specialized pipeline designed to process ONT long reads either solely or in combination with short reads (hybrid assembly). This pipeline relies on a dual approach that uses both assembly-based and assembly-free strategies. Particularly, EasyNanoMeta incorporates four assemblers (metaFlye¹¹⁶, OPERA-MS¹¹⁷, metaSPAdes³⁵, MetaPlatanus¹¹⁸), five binners (SemiBin2²¹, MetaBAT2³, MaxBin2⁵, CONCOCT⁴, VAMB⁸⁸) and a polishing tool (NextPolish¹¹⁹) to assure the best possible outcome. Additionally, once the bins are obtained, it performs the common tasks such as functional annotation with Prokka⁵⁸, quality control with CheckM2²⁴, phylogeny inference with PhyloPhlan¹²⁰ and taxonomic classification with GTDB-Tk2²⁵. For the assembly-free methodology, EasyNanoMeta provides a full report containing composition, diversity and correlation among the identified species with Kraken2¹¹ and Centrifuge¹²¹. Regarding operational characteristics, this pipeline can be run automatically on a Singularity/Apptainer image that streamlines the setup process and minimizes dependency issues or experienced users can execute individual modules through shell scripts that rely on Conda environments.

2.2 Hi-Fi-MAG-Pipeline¹²²

Hi-Fi-MAG is a simple, yet time-saving pipeline developed and maintained by Pacific Biosciences specially designed to build MAGs from Hi-Fi reads (long PacBio reads). It encompasses different binning tools (MetaBAT2³ and SemiBin2²¹) along with DASTool⁷ as refinement software; CheckM2²⁴ serves a quality control tool, where contigs above 500 kb are kept as single bins if they show a completeness above 93%, otherwise they are sent back to the binning module. This approach enhances the recovery of high-quality and single-contig MAGs, outperforming traditional binning methods. After MAG de-replication, taxonomic annotation is achieved with GTDB-Tk2²⁵, and a complete graphical report is compiled automatically. One important caveat about this workflow is represented by its lack of assembly step, and hence the user must prepare the assembly of the PacBio sequences beforehand using tools such as hifiasm¹²³ in its meta version, metaFlye¹¹⁶, OPERA-MS¹¹⁷,

among others. Hi-Fi-MAG-Pipeline requires Conda as software manager, and it is orchestrated by Snakemake⁶¹.

2.3 Mapler¹²⁴

Mapler is a pipeline specifically designed to handle PacBio HiFi long reads. Mapler workflow is orchestrated by Snakemake along with Conda for package management, enabling scalable execution on local or cluster systems. Regarding the specific tools encompassed by Mapler, state-of-the-art assemblers such as metaMDBG¹²⁵, hifiasm-meta¹²³, metaFlye¹¹⁶ and OPERA-MS¹¹⁷ are available, with MetaBAT2³ as the binning tool. Later on the workflow, each bin is classified taxonomically via GTDB-Tk2²⁵ or Kraken2¹¹, and genome quality is evaluated using CheckM2²⁴ standards. Mapler aligns reads back to contigs with Minimap2⁹⁴ to compute novel metrics including the aligned read percentage and aligned base percentage, stratified across quality categories. It is important to mention that Mapler accepts assemblies and bins as input to skip part of the process, and it includes a parallel analysis, where assembled versus unassembled reads are contrasted by evaluating k-mer distributions (KAT¹²⁶), read quality (FastQC²⁸), and taxonomic composition (Kraken2 + Krona⁴¹). As a result, by combining classic bin-based metrics with read-to-contig alignment statistics, Mapler assists in estimating how much of the sequence diversity remains uncaptured.

2.4 NanoPhase¹²⁷

NanoPhase is a pipeline that enables building high-quality MAGs from ONT long reads, optionally enhanced with short read-based MAG polishing. The backbone of the pipeline is represented by an assembly with metaFlye¹¹⁶ followed by contig binning with MetaBAT2³ and MaxBin2⁵, and bin refinement with a MetaWRAP²³ module. To estimate abundance and coverage, the contigs are mapped against the reads, and several polishing rounds with Racon¹²⁸ and medaka, complete the workflow to generate high-accuracy final bins; If the user decides to include short reads in the analysis, these are used for polishing with Pilon¹²⁹. Complementary, MetaQuast⁹³ and CheckM⁶⁴ v1.0 are in charge of MAG quality control, IDEEL¹³⁰ evaluates the fraction of predicted full-length proteins in each MAG, full-length proteins are detected via alignment with UniProtKB¹³¹, and Prokka⁵⁸ serves as functional annotation software. Remarkably, NanoPhase allows prophage and active prophage identification within the reconstructed MAGs with VIBRANT¹³² and PropagAtE¹³³. Among pipeline technical specifications, this pipeline requires Conda as package manager and it offers parallelized execution with GNU Parallel to speed up the analysis.

3. Dual pipelines

3.1 GEN-ERA¹³⁴

GEN-ERA suite is a collection of Nextflow⁹ pipelines aiming at supporting MAG reconstruction and annotation with as many methodologies as possible starting from either short or long reads. Specifically, this toolbox counts with more than 10 workflows specifically designed for tasks ranging from assembly and binning, quality assessment and decontamination, orthologous inference and maximum likelihood phylogenomic analyses, SSU rRNA phylogeny (constrained by ribosomal phylogenomic), Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) clustering, taxonomic identification and metabolic modelling. Moreover, GEN-ERA incorporates specific tools designed to handle eukaryotic assembly annotation such as BRAKER2¹³⁵ and AMAW¹³⁶. Thus, GEN-ERA suits almost all requirements any user might demand given the variety of goals that can be achieved within a single software suite. From a technical point of view, operational GEN-ERA features, Nextflow-managed and Singularity-executed, ensures portability and reproducibility across environments.

3.2 Metagenomics-Toolkit¹³⁷

Metagenomics-Toolkit is a workflow designed to increase scalability of task execution, enabling optimal resource allocation from its machine learning-optimized assembly step. This optimized assembly tailors the peak RAM value requested by a metagenome assembler to match actual requirements, thereby minimizing the dependency on dedicated high-memory hardware.

Metagenomics-Toolkit is wrapped by Nextflow⁹ and powered with Docker containerization technology, and it can take either short or Oxford Nanopore (ONT) long reads as input. As a result, this pipeline is highly scalable and adaptable across computational infrastructures with a backbone workflow that relies on the traditional MAG-aimed steps such as quality control, assembly, binning, and annotation, plus an aggregation module that captures the output from each sample to “polish” the final MAGs. Regarding special features offered by Metagenomics-Toolkit, it offers plasmid identification based on various tools, the recovery of unassembled microbial community members, and the discovery of microbial interdependencies through a combination of dereplication, co-occurrence, and genome-scale metabolic modeling.

3.3 metaWGS¹³⁸

metaWGS is one of the most recently released pipelines whose main differential is related with the possibility to assemble either short reads or long sequences (PacBio). This Nextflow⁹ pipeline is built off Singularity with consequent benefits this kind of setup brings as discussed previously. It incorporates a wide variety of tools as it must ensure a proper workflow for both types of sequencing technologies in a traditional end-to-end framework divided into 8 steps. The first step aims at cleaning and performing quality control with proper tools according to the input, while the second step allows the assembly of the sequences using either metaSPAdes³⁵/MEGAHIT¹⁶ for short sequences and hifiasm¹²³/metaFlye¹¹⁶ for PacBio reads. Following with the process, this pipeline filters the contigs and performs structural annotation during steps 3 and 4, respectively; step 5 is designed to estimate contig abundance by mapping them against the reads. Afterwards, a complete subworkflow for functional annotation is undergone with eggNOG-mapper⁶⁷ at its core (step 6), and contig taxonomic affiliation is achieved through *home-made* scripts (step 7) to conclude with step 8, where the contigs are binned with MaxBin2⁵, MetaBAT2³ and CONCOCT⁴. Furthermore, metaWGS utilizes Binette¹³⁹, a state-of-the-art binning refinement tool designed to construct high-quality MAGs from the output of multiple binning tools. As a special remark, metaWGS performs read taxonomic profiling via Kaiju, as well as contig annotation that includes an in-house algorithm and mapping against the reads.

3.4 MG-TK¹⁴⁰

MG-TK (Metagenomic Toolkit) performs read assembly (SPAdes⁵⁷, MEGAHIT¹⁶, Flye¹⁴¹, metaMDBG¹²⁵) and binning (MetaBAT2³, SemiBin2²¹, MetaDecoder¹⁴²), gene prediction, and clustering into nonredundant gene catalogs, followed by abundance estimation and functional annotation. It is structured around three main phases: processing raw sequences, building a gene catalog, and reconstructing species from MAGs with downstream phylogenetic analyses. It produces a wide range of outputs, including assemblies, MAGs, gene predictions, SNP calls and mapping outputs. A special remark MG-TK exhibits is its ability to generate detailed abundance matrices for both taxonomic and functional features, with hierarchical summaries available at multiple levels. The taxonomic profiles are reported using GTDB¹⁴³ lineages, while functional annotations are provided for major databases such as KEGG¹⁴⁴, SEED¹⁴⁵, CAZY¹⁴⁶, eggNOG⁴⁵, and TCDB¹⁴⁷. MG-TK also estimates completeness of functional modules, such as KEGG pathways, and links genes to multiple annotations for deeper exploration by the user. Beyond gene catalogs, MG-TK integrates MAG/MGS (Metagenomics Species) information, associating MAGs with their metagenomic species and providing detailed gene content, including representative MAGs for each species. Additionally, MG-TK can provide assembly-independent profiles via a wide variety of tools including riboFinder¹⁴⁸, MetaPhlAn⁴⁷ and mOTUs¹⁰².

3.5 VEBA¹⁴⁹

VEBA (Viral Eukaryotic Bacterial Archaeal) is a Conda-executed pipeline designed that enables the recovery and classification of genomes from all domains of life including archaeas, prokaryotes, microeukaryotes, and viruses. It starts with a common short read-preprocessing and assembly from which the process is bifurcated for prokaryotic and viral binning; unbinned contigs from the viral module are reincorporated into the prokaryotic contig set. Residual contigs from the prokaryotic module are then considered for eukaryotic MAG generation to proceed with the annotation and classification covering the genomes obtained in each module. Hence, several databases are

considered at this step such as UniRef50/90¹⁵⁰, MIBiG¹⁵¹, VFDB⁴⁹, CAZy¹⁴⁶, KOfamKOALA⁸⁶, Pfam¹⁵², NCBIfam-AMR¹⁵³ and AntiFam¹⁵⁴. Also, a joint phylogeny is obtained based on MAG-gene models and lineage marker detection. An interesting approach VEBA follows is represented by the module *coverage.py* that collects all the unbinned contigs, from viral, eukaryotic and prokaryotic steps, to pursue a pseudo-coassembly, where iteratively the reference fasta (built from the contigs) and the sorted BAM files used as a final pass through prokaryotic and eukaryotic binning modules. This pseudo-coassembly approach is optional, being easily enabled during the workflow execution; the pipeline documentation widely discusses when this type of assembly should be used in specific cases. Notably, VEBA automates the detection of candidate phyla radiation (CPR) bacteria and integrates a consensus microeukaryotic database to optimize gene modeling and taxonomic classification.

4. Hybrid pipelines

4.1 Aviary¹⁵⁵

Aviary is a modular, Snakemake⁶¹-based pipeline, with Conda as package manager, designed for single or hybrid metagenomic assembly and MAG recovery, supporting both short and long-read input sequences. The workflow is distributed in 8 modules following a traditional workflow starting with quality and diversity assessment of the reads, followed by a discriminated assembly according to the type of input, MEGAHIT¹⁶ or metaSPAdes³⁵ for short reads only or metaFlye¹¹⁶ in case of long reads solely. For hybrid assembly the process is divided into four stages: polishing with Racon¹²⁸ and Pilon¹²⁹, metrics-based filtering, assembly and discard of low-quality bins and re-assembly with Unicycler¹⁵⁶. The pipeline proceeds with a subsequent assembly evaluation in terms of fragmentation, misassembly detection and diversity quantification, and a complementary module moves forward with a read mapping of the assembly and abundance statistics calculation. To continue with the workflow, the contigs are binned using up to 6 tools (MetaBAT2³, Rosella¹⁵⁷, MetaBAT1⁷¹, VAMB⁸⁸, MaxBin2⁵ and CONCOCT⁴) and refined afterwards with 5-time loop that includes CheckM2²⁴, Rosella Refine and DASTool⁷. The pipeline ends with MAG recovery assessment via CoverM¹⁰⁶, CheckM2 and SingleM to proceed with MAG annotation through GTDB-Tk2²⁵, Prodigal³⁹ and eggNOG⁴⁵. Variant calling, ANI analysis and genotype recovery with Lorikeet¹⁵⁸ are interesting attributes offered by Aviary as a complement to the traditional genomic feature detection. Aviary's design presents a series of advantages that include the possibility of running modules, multi-sample handling and scalability across different computational infrastructures.

4.2 MUFFIN¹⁵⁹

MUFFIN is a reproducible pipeline built with Nextflow⁹ designed for hybrid assembly by integrating short-read (Illumina) and long-read (nanopore) sequencing data. MUFFIN begins its workflow with a quality control of the reads (fastp⁵³ and FilTlong) to progress through hybrid assembly (metaSPAdes³⁵ or metaFlye¹¹⁶ with polishing) and differential binning (CONCOCT⁴, MetaBAT2³, and MaxBin2⁵). After bin refining with the MetaWRAP²³ refinement module, a hybrid reassembly is pursued with Unicycler¹⁵⁶. The pipeline ends with bin classification through CheckM⁶⁴ v1.1 and sourmash¹³ (combined with GTDB¹⁴³), and with bin annotation with eggNOG⁴⁵ and a KEGG¹⁴⁴ parser, providing high-quality, annotated MAGs and insights into the metabolic potential of the microbial community. Optionally, the user can provide metatranscriptomics data to perform a de novo transcript assembly (Trinity¹⁶⁰), quantification (Salmon¹⁶¹) and annotation (eggNOG). Additionally, given its modularity design, the workflow can start as well with user-provided bins, differential reads or only RNA-seq data. MUFFIN can be executed with either Conda or Docker, and its native Nextflow features confer to it the possibility to restart the pipeline in case of failing, run on different computing infrastructures, multi-sample handling, among others.

4.3 nf-core/mag¹⁶²

nf-core/mag is a Nextflow⁹ pipeline developed following the nf-core guidelines that ensures robustness and reproducibility. It supports both short-read and long-read sequences, as well as hybrid datasets, and it leverages a modular design, containerization (Docker, Singularity, among others) and

package managers (Conda) to confer portability across different computing environments, including HPC and cloud systems. Beyond these important features, as part of the workflow orchestration, `nf-core/mag` can handle multi-sample input, it can be restarted if it is interrupted at any point thanks to its native checkpoint control and different assembly/binning modes can be selected. This pipeline encompasses tools for quality control of the reads (Porechop¹⁶³, Filtlong¹⁶⁴, NanoPack2¹⁶⁵, fastp⁵³), host removal (Bowtie2¹⁰), adapter trimming (AdapterRemoval¹⁶⁶), and several assemblers (MEGAHIT¹⁶, metaSPAdes³⁵, Flye¹⁴¹, metaMDBG¹²⁵, hybridSPAdes¹⁶⁷). In addition, it offers three binning software options (MetaBAT2³, MaxBin2⁵ and CONCOCT⁴) along with an optional refinement tool (DASTool⁷). `nf-core/mag` checks assembly and bin quality through several tools that include CheckM2²⁴, MetaQUAST⁹³, BUSCO⁸⁹ and GUNC⁹⁰, and for genome annotation, it uses GTDB-Tk2²⁵ or CAT¹⁶⁸ (taxonomic) and Prokka⁵⁸ or MetaEuk¹⁶⁹ (functional). As special features, this pipeline can carry out a taxonomic annotation of the sequences (Kraken2¹¹ and Centrifuge¹²¹), validates the presence of typical ancient DNA damages (PyDamage¹⁷⁰), attempts MAG domain classification with Tiara¹⁷¹ and identifies viruses after assembly with geNomad¹⁷². After workflow execution, `nf-core/mag` generates detailed multi-sample summaries through MultiQC⁵⁴, and it creates HTML reports to track resource usage. Finally, the `nf-core` framework is actively maintained and updated as it relies on a numerous and enthusiastic developing community.

4.4 ngs-preprocess-MpGAP-Bacannot¹⁷³

Ngs-preprocess, MpGAP and Bacannot are a series of Nextflow⁹-based and container-powered pipelines designed to achieve a wide variety of specific tasks. `ngs-preprocess` performs several quality-control steps required for Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) data assessment, while `MpGAP` supports de novo genome assembly from Illumina, PacBio, and ONT reads, enabling short-read, long-read, and hybrid assemblies using tools like metaSPAdes³⁵, metaFlye¹¹⁶, Canu¹⁷⁴, and Unicycler¹⁵⁶, followed by polishing and quality assessment. Meanwhile, `Bacannot` provides an annotation workflow that incorporates gene prediction, rRNA detection, sequence typing, KEGG-based metabolic reconstruction, and secondary metabolite identification, integrating tools such as Prokka⁵⁸, Bakt¹⁷⁵, Barnmap¹⁰⁹, MLST¹⁷⁶, KofamScan⁸⁶, KEGGDecoder¹⁷⁷, and antiSMASH¹⁷⁸. As an additional analytical procedure, `Bacannot` incorporates additional support for methylation analysis via Nanopolish¹⁷⁹. Noticeably, this set of pipelines do not include at any point neither contig binning nor bin quality assessment; however, the smooth interconnection among the pipelines makes them an interesting option for metagenome assembly and annotation, boosted by the native benefits conferred by Nextflow and container technology.

4.5 SqueezeMeta¹⁸⁰

SqueezeMeta is a fully automatic pipeline written in Perl scripts that relies on Conda for software execution. As special features, this pipeline can handle short and long reads (ONT and Hi-Fi) in both single or hybrid approaches, supports for de-novo metatranscriptome assembly and hybrid metagenomics/metatranscriptomics analysis, carries out taxonomic annotation of unassembled reads, and empowers the user with a GUI application for downstream analysis. Also, SqueezeMeta's flexibility enables different assembly modes such as *sequential* (samples assembled individually), *co-assembly* (samples assembled ensemble), *merged* (samples assembled individually with a posterior pooling) and *seqmerge* (similar to merged with a guided pooling based on assembly similarity). This pipeline follows the traditional workflow by applying quality filtering and trimming with Trimmomatic²⁷, then the reads are assembled by MEGAHIT¹⁶ and SPAdes (rnaSPAdes¹⁸¹, Canu¹⁷⁴ and metaFlye¹¹⁶ are run if transcriptomics or long read data are provided) to be binned afterwards with MaxBin2⁵, MetaBAT2³ and CONCOCT⁴; DASTool⁷ is in charge of bin refinement. MAG Quality checks are established through CheckM2²⁴, and optionally taxonomic classification is achieved by GTDB-Tk2²⁵. To complement MAG annotation with KEGG¹⁴⁴ and MetaCyc¹⁸², SqueezeMeta analyzes the assembly by performing an homology searching against taxonomic and functional databases, an HMMER search against Pfam¹⁵² database, and an estimation of taxa and function abundances. An important remark of this pipeline is its numerous and helpful developing and maintaining community.

5. Web-based pipelines with external computational resource support

5.1 BV-BRC¹⁸³

BV-BRC (Bacterial and Viral Bioinformatics Resource Center) is a web-based platform that supports a broad spectrum of microbial genomics analyses, including genome-resolved metagenomics. This platform offers an intuitive interface to perform tailored quality control, assembly, binning, annotation, and downstream comparative analyses. For MAG building, BV-BRC has developed a specific metagenomic binning service, which offers genome assembly with metaSPAdes³⁵ or MEGAHIT¹⁶ and a customized approach for genome binning based on kmer distribution and multi-genome functionality. Moreover, BV-BRC leverages PATRIC¹⁸⁴ genomes to create reference bins as a starting point for annotation with RASTtk¹⁸⁵ and/or VIGOR4¹⁸⁶. Regarding technical features, BV-BRC runs entirely on a remote infrastructure, allowing users to execute workflows without local installations or advanced computational setups. Aside from the features already mentioned, customizable analysis jobs, visualization tools and integrated comparative genomics tools are available, making BV-BRC a valuable resource for users seeking an accessible, reproducible, and data-rich environment for metagenomic studies.

5.2 Galaxy¹⁸⁷

Galaxy is a web-based platform and open-source project that empowers scientists all over the world to conduct bioinformatics analysis in a user-friendly and intuitive graphical interface that requires no programming skills. Galaxy offers a broad range of tools covering genomics, transcriptomics, metagenomics, among many others, where the user is free to select the software that best suits their needs. In addition, the users can share their workflows in the platform, and therefore users can just follow pre-established methodologies validated by a world-wide community. As a result, there are multiple pipelines designed for MAG reconstruction that feature common tools like MEGAHIT¹⁶ for assembly, MetaBAT2³ or MaxBin2⁵ for binning, and Prokka⁵⁸ or GTDB-Tk2²⁵ for annotation and classification. Also, given Galaxy's flexibility the traditional workflow can be expanded to include long reads, accomplish read-based taxonomic profiling or detect and classify viral sequences. Being so, Galaxy ensures reproducibility through automatic tracking of parameters and tool versions, and supports HPC and cloud deployment, making it scalable for projects of various sizes. Notwithstanding, the users may experience limitations in performance for large datasets and/or delays in result processing as Galaxy's community of users grows every day with the subsequent demand for more computational resources.

5.3 IDseq¹⁸⁸

IDseq is an open-source, cloud-based platform developed for metagenomic next-generation sequencing (mNGS) analysis. IDseq has a specific scope focused on pathogen detection, antibiotic resistance detection and infection control. IDseq supports short-reads or long reads (ONT) to provide analyses that encompass host read removal, quality control, alignment, and taxonomic classification using a curated reference database based on NCBI³¹ nt and nr databases. Although IDseq is not primarily focused on MAG reconstruction, it is highly valuable in the initial stages of metagenomics data analysis projects. As interesting remarks, IDseq's results are visualized through interactive dashboards that provide taxonomic trees, abundance plots, and detailed sample metrics thanks to its web-based interface that requires minimal bioinformatics expertise. Also, the users can find alternative pipelines for viral consensus genome recovery and antimicrobial resistance gene detection.

5.4 IMG/M¹⁸⁹

IMG/M (Integrated Microbial Genomes & Microbiomes) developed by the DOE (the United States Department Of Energy) Joint Genome Institute for the annotation and comparative analysis of microbial genomes and metagenomes. IMG/M is designed primarily to host and annotate genomes, offering a pipeline, running on their servers, that takes contigs to bin them via SemiBin2²¹, with subsequent quality control by CheckM⁶⁴. The taxonomic annotation is given by GTDB-Tk⁷², and functional annotation is supported using resources such as KEGG¹⁹⁰, COGs¹⁹¹, Pfam¹⁵² and

TIGRFAMs¹⁹², enabling pathway reconstruction and metabolic profiling; as inferred from this workflow description, the users need to perform the assemble step elsewhere. This platform also incorporates comparative tools to allow exploration of gene content, pathway coverage, phylogenetic profiles, and functional similarities across datasets. It is important to mention that datasets submitted to IMG/M are initially private but must eventually become public. IMG/M enforces an embargo period, after which annotated data are released and cannot be withdrawn, although updates are allowed.

5.4 KBase¹⁹³

KBase (the United States Department Of Energy Systems Biology Knowledgebase) is a collaborative, web-based platform that enables researchers to perform comprehensive metagenomics analyses through its customized interactive Narrative Interface. This platform allows users to build and share workflows (narratives) for genome assembly, comparative genomics, metagenomics, among others. Specifically, the metagenomics narrative offers running MAG-centered pipeline steps such as quality control, assembly (e.g., metaSPAdes³⁵, MEGAHIT¹⁶), binning (i.e., MetaBAT2³), annotation (e.g., RASTtk¹⁸⁵, DRAM⁹¹), and metabolic modeling using ModelSEED¹⁹⁴. KBase platform offers automated data provenance, seamless integration with public databases, and interactive visualizations to interpret MAG quality, taxonomy, and metabolic pathways. The possibility of running analyses using external resources makes KBase a powerful and accessible environment for genome-resolved metagenomics, particularly valuable for users lacking access to HPC systems.

5.5 MGnify¹⁹⁵

MGnify is a web-based platform hosted by EMBL-EBI with an automatized service for submitting and annotating microbiome-derived sequence data. It counts with a standardized pipeline that receives raw reads to perform functional and taxonomic annotation with an extensive series of tools encompassing mOTUs2⁸⁴, InterProScan⁵⁹, KEGG annotation (hmmscan¹⁹⁶), eggNOG-mapper⁶⁷ and/or antiSMASH¹⁷⁸. Optionally, MGnify offers the possibility for read assembly through metaSPAdes with a prior contamination removal to continue with the annotation. In the recent years, MGnify has evolved to accept and process long reads from PacBio and ONT with the pipeline MGnify-lr that carries out read pre-filtering, assembly with Flye and re-mapping against the initial sequences. Furthermore, users can contribute to the resource MGnify Genomes which stores a genome catalogues each user can create with their own MAGs. Once the MAGs are submitted to this space, they are automatically analyzed with a pipeline that establishes overall quality and annotates them. Given that MGnify is a service controlled by EMBL-EBI, the user is only requested to submit the data and make it publicly available before the analysis to ENA. As a result, MGnify is a powerful computational resource and user-friendly as the user interacts with the platform to upload the data through its web interface, taking the burden off the user. However, MGnify's reliance on predefined workflows may limit flexibility for users seeking to customize specific steps or parameters in the analysis, while at the same time heavy use by multiple users may delay result delivery.

5.6 WGS2+/LoRA¹⁹⁷

The Nephele suite offers two independent metagenomics analysis pipelines: WGS2+ for short-read data and LoRA to handle PacBio or ONT reads. Briefly, WGS2+ performs quality control and host removal using tools such as fastp⁵³ and Kraken2¹¹, assembles reads with metaSPAdes³⁵, and optionally bins contigs into MAGs with MetaBAT2³, assessing MAG quality with CheckM⁶⁴. Taxonomic classification is achieved through Kraken2, whilst eggNOG-mapper⁶⁷ is in charge of functional annotation. LoRA, on its side, uses metaFlye¹¹⁶ for assembly, integrates the same binning and functional annotation tools, and expands the classification module with inclusion of GTDB-Tk²⁵ and CheckM2²⁴. Both pipelines can generate taxonomic profiles, functional summaries and detect antibiotic resistance genes through Nephele's user-friendly cloud interface; WGS2+ supports metatranscriptome assembly from RNA-seq data. As a result, WGS2+/LoRA represent a great option for users who are experienced at command line tool execution or with limited local computing resources. However, Nephele's platform usage is limited as it relies on AWS for software execution, and therefore users receive a fixed number of *use codes*, and in case of intensive resource demands, they can request extended access.

6. Special pipelines

6.1 Pipeline for ancient DNA¹⁹⁸

MAG recovery from ancient DNA can be challenging due to DNA intrinsic properties such as degradation, fragmentation, chemical damage, low-abundance and contamination. Nonetheless, a validated pipeline to manage this type of data is proposed by Standeven *et al.* (2024)¹⁹⁸, where the MAGs are obtained by following the classic steps involving quality check, decontamination, assembly, binning, bin quality assessment and refinement, and taxonomic annotation. The main advantage of this pipeline is the integration of different bin software, and it can also authenticate the sequence provenance by estimating damage authentication of the host DNA (mainly human) via mapDamage2¹⁹⁹. Despite its validation to recover high-quality MAGs, this pipeline is only proposed, and it has not been properly compiled in a single repository or container, and hence users should run the tools manually or leverage any of the other available pipelines in this suite.

6.2 Eukfinder²⁰⁰

Eukfinder is a specialized pipeline designed to recover microbial eukaryotic genomes, including both nuclear and mitochondrial DNA. Considering the inherent complexity and underrepresentation of eukaryotic genomes in metagenomics, this tool is composed by two workflows: the first one for Illumina short reads (Eukfinder_short) and another one for assembled contigs or long-read data (Eukfinder_long). In the workflow for short reads, they are first classified into five major taxonomic groups using Centrifuge¹²¹ and PLAST²⁰¹, and afterwards 'Eukaryotic' and 'Unknown' reads are subsequently assembled and reclassified to refine candidate eukaryotic sequences. On the other hand, the long-read version focuses on classifying pre-assembled contigs before proceeding to genome binning and downstream analysis. The binning procedure is common to both approaches and it relies on MyCC²⁰² output, Centrifuge¹²¹, and PLAST results in customized and tailored integration of kmer analysis and contigs mapping to eukaryotic genomes. Given its specificity, Eukfinder represents a flexible solution for studying eukaryotic microbial communities in environmental metagenomics.

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